

Self-improving Workflow Models for Generating Combinatorial Objects Designed in the Kepler Project System

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Abstract

In this paper we consider the problem of designing a self-improving meta-model of job workflow that is sensitive to the change of the computational environment. As an example of searched combinatorial objects permutations and some classes of integral graphs are used. We propose a number of dedicated methods that can improve the execution time of workflow based on decision trees and the replication of some actors in the workflow.

1. Introduction

Let $G = (V, E)$ denote a *simple graph* with a nonempty vertex set V of a cardinality $n = |V|$, and a set of pairs of vertices called edges E where loops are forbidden. The *valency matrix* ($D(G) = \text{diag}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n)$) of the graph G is a diagonal matrix where d_i is a degree of the vertex i . The *distance matrix* ($\text{Dis}(G)$) of G is the all-pairs shortest path matrix consisting of distances between all pairs of vertices in the graph G . The set $Sp(G) = \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n\}$ of graph eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix A is called the *spectrum* of graph G . The *Laplacian matrix* $L(G)$ is defined as $L := D - A$. The *unsigned Laplacian matrix* of the graph G is defined as $|L| := D + A$.

The generation of combinatorial objects like graphs always has a natural barrier of the time complexity connected with the size of search space. We are often also interested in calculating some invariants of graphs that can separate them into disjointed classes. We can observe that generation algorithms that are fast for graphs with small values of vertices can work very long when n grows. For some purposes also adjacency matrices of graphs can be split and distributed on hosts. This is connected with some overhead, but can improve computation time.

Fig. 1: The model of computation (\circ : A – Actors; \diamond : R – Relations, \blacktriangledown : InP – Input ports; \blacktriangle : OutP – Output ports)

The workflow model of computation is a bipartite digraph $W = (A \cup R \cup \text{InP} \cup \text{OutP}, LP \cup LR)$, where A is a set of Actors (units that can perform some computation; in particular Composite Actors). The set R contains vertices that correspond to relations. InP is a set of input ports and OutP is a set of output ports, respectively. LP is a set of pairs (a, p) where $a \in A$, and $p \in \text{InP} \cup \text{OutP}$. LR is a set of pairs (r, p) where $r \in R$, and $i \in \text{InP} \cup \text{OutP}$. It is forbidden when LP contains more than one pair (r, p) where $r \in R$, and $p \in \text{InP}$. The

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workflow shown in Fig. 1 represents a simple pipeline workflow: the output from A1 is the input for A2; the output of A2 is the input for A3. The relations R1 and R2 correspond to the arrow. Directions of the arrows can be obtained by the analysis of existing paths in the graph W.

The main goal of this paper is to describe possibilities of transforming workflows in a such a way that the runtime of a new one should be shorter than the old one. Therefore we define some meta-workflows that can take some statistic data of executions of a set of workflows and choose the best one, or define a decision tree which workflow use for a specific values of parameters of the combinatorial problem to solve. Usually, when programmers define a workflow, it is tested only on a computational environment. Thus, even if some statistical data are taken to build decision trees then it can happen that for other (i.e. new computers with different processors and memory sizes), those trees make wrong decisions. To avoid this situation we can again use meta-workflow for getting new statistic data and build new decision trees or try using techniques which correct threshold values in the current decision tree.

2. Modeling Markup Language in the Kepler Project

The Kepler Project is freely available under the BSD License. It is based on the Ptolemy II System, a platform supporting multiple models of computation (MoC), i.e.: Synchronous Data Flow (SDF), Dynamic Data Flow (DDF), Process Network (PN), Discrete Events (DE), and Continuous Time (CT). The Kepler Project provides a graphical user interface and a run-time engine that can execute workflows either from within the graphical interface or from a command line. Workflows can be nested, allowing complex tasks to be composed from simpler components. Kepler Project workflows and customized components can be saved and reused using their own archive format (KAR). The KAR file, is a zipped catalogue where the sub-catalogue META-INF contains the file MANIFEST.MF, and the XML file stores an information about Directors, Actors, Relations and other workflow details and the documentation. The format of these XML files is defined by the Modeling Markup Language (MoML) [3]. In the MoML file also properties how to render and visualize the workflow is included. The main element in every MoML file is a property called Director. One of them is the SDF Director (cf. Listing 1) corresponding to the Synchronous Data Flow.

```
<property name="SDF Director" class="ptolemy.domains.sdf.kernel.SDFDirector">
...
</property>
```

Listing 1: The property describing a Director in the Kepler Project workflow

The Kepler Project ships with a searchable library containing over 350 ready-to-use processing components (Actors) that can be easily customized, connected and then run from a desktop environment. For example we can put in the MoML file the Constant and the MonitorValue Actors (cf. Listing 2).

```
<entity name="Constant" class="ptolemy.actor.lib.Const" />
<entity name="Monitor Value" class="ptolemy.actor.lib.gui.MonitorValue" />
```

Listing 2: The entities describing a *Constant* Actor and a *Monitor Value* Actor in the Kepler Project workflow

Usually Actors have a nonempty set of input and output Ports. The names of Ports are unique in the whole MoML file (cf. Listing 3). Types of data that are carried out by Ports can be predefined or not described (i.e. integer, double, float, array of integers).

```
<port name="input" class="ptolemy.actor.TypedIOPort" />
<port name="output" class="ptolemy.actor.TypedIOPort" />
```

Listing 3: Introducing Ports in the Kepler Project workflow

If we would like to connect the output Port of the Constant Actor and the input Port of the Monitor Value Actor we need to introduce into the MoML file the element called Relation (cf. Listing 4). The names of relations are unique. The value of the attribute Port in the link element describe the name of Actor and the name of Port separated by a dot.

```
<relation name="relation" class="ptolemy.actor.TypedIORelation" />
<link port="Constant.output" relation="relation"/>
<link port="Monitor Value.input" relation="relation"/>
```

Listing 4: Connecting Actors by the Relation using links in the Kepler Project workflow

An example of the workflow that during the execution copies the value 1 from the *Constant* Actor to the *Monitor Value* Actor is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: The Kepler Project workflow with the SDF Director and two Actors: *Constant* and *Monitor Value*

In the Kepler Project there are Actors that, can help transform XML data. It can be useful, when we try to generate set of workflows or to transform old workflow into a new one.

3. Directors and Actors in the Kepler Project

In the Kepler Project there are 5 types of Directors that are responsible for controlling executions of workflows (SDF, DDF, PN, DE, CT). There are many Actors that can perform different tasks. It is also possible to use Composite Actors. For simple calculations we can use the Expression Actor (cf. Figure 3). This Actor is using the Ptolemy II expression language. Sometimes in this paper an Expression Actor in workflow examples is a representative of a time consuming algorithm.

Fig. 3: An example of the simple calculation with the *Expression* Actor

Using different Actors we can display output in new windows (the *Display* Actor) or/and write the same output to a file using the *File Writer* Actor (cf. Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Writing some output to a file in the Kepler Project workflow

The Python Actor can be used for some more complicated calculations (cf. Figure 5 and Listing 7).

Fig. 5: Usage the *Python* Actor in the Kepler Project workflow

The implementation in the Python language shown in Listing 5 uses the Ptolemy library to convert the input token into x variable, and then converts the calculated value $x*x$ into the output token.

```

import ptolemy.data
class Main :
    "Calculating square of x"
    def fire(self) :
        x = self.input.get(0).intValue()
        self.output.send(0, ptolemy.data.IntToken(x*x))
    return

```

Listing 5: The implementation of the Main function in the Python Actor

The Kepler Project workflow can also use *RExpression* Actors that use the R Project System for the calculation [4] (cf. Figure 6).

Fig. 6: Usage the *RExpression* Actor in the Kepler Project workflow

The corresponding implementation in the R Project language is shown in Listing 6. The name of Ports *x* (InP) and *f* (OutP) are mapped on internal variables.

```
f <- x*x
```

Listing 6: The implementation calculating square value of *x* in the *RExpression* Actor

In the workflow we can use some external programmes for calculation (cf. Figure 7). The output string can be converted to an integer value using the *String to Int* Actor. If we wish to run a programme on the different host we can use the *SSH to Execute* Actor similarly to using the *External Execution* Actor.

Fig. 7: Usage the *External Execution* Actor in the Kepler Project workflow

The Kepler Project workflow can also be easily connected with the functionality of some web-services.

Fig. 8: Usage the *File Reader* Actor and the web-service for calculating the square value of $x = 3$

In Listing 7 there is the Prolog implementation of a web-service used in the example shown in Figure 8 for calculating the square value of $x = 3$. To run this web-service locally on the $port = 5000$ we use the command `server(5000)`.

```

square(X, Y) :- Y is X * X.
:- use_module(library(http/thread_httpd)).
:- use_module(library(http/http_dispatch)).
:- use_module(library(http/http_parameters)).
:- http_handler(root(square), answer, []).
server(Port) :- http_server(http_dispatch, [port(Port)]).
answer(Request) :-
    http_parameters(Request, [x(X, [integer])]),
    format('Content-type: text/plain~n~n'),
    square(X,Y),
    format('square(~w) = ~w~n', [X, Y]).

```

Listing 7: The file square.pl - the Prolog implementation of the web-service that calculates the square value of x

In the Kepler Project workflows can be hierarchical. For this purposes *Composite Actors* are used as is shown in Figure 9. The sub-workflow that map input and output ports of the *Composite Actor* is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 9: Usage the *Composite Actor*

Composite Actors can be useful in the case when different variants of algorithms doing the same jobs are available and/or some conversions of input or output data types are necessary.

Fig. 10: The workflow of the *composite Actor* from the Figure 9

In the Kepler Project we can also implement in the Java programming language new Directors and Actors. The Kepler Project workflow can also be used for some tests, i.e. if we would like to check if two or more algorithms are equivalent (cf. Figure 11).

Fig. 11: Testing two variants of the algorithm

4. Getting statistic about the runtime and workflow working modes

The Kepler Provenance add-on module suite provides and allows the recording of workflow execution history into a database. Using the meta-model shown in Figure 12 we can obtain the graph with a time execution of some programs (or Actors). This meta-model is rather an illustration of an idea how this can be measured, but not the precise time of given program execution because firing Actors in the Kepler Project done by the Director can be realized in a different order (so, in some cases the runtime can be measured as negative). A better idea is to have in the Actor an extra Port where the runtime of the last execution is available.

```
#include <stdio.h>
int main() { int i,j,n, y;
scanf("%d",&n);
for (i=0;i<n;i++) for (j=0;j<n;j++){ y = i*i*i*i; }
printf("%d",n);
return 0;
}
```

Listing 17: The file p1.c - the example of the algorithm with the complexity equal to $O(n^2)$.

Figure 12 depicts the meta-workflow that uses two *WallClockTime* Actors to get the difference in the runtime of the *p1.exe* algorithm. The source code of this program is shown in Listing 17.

Fig. 12: The meta-workflow for getting the statistic information about runtimes of a given program (*p1.exe*) in the function of task size.

The execution time of the *p1.exe* algorithm in the function of input parameter is shown by the *Sequence Plotter* Actor (cf. Figure 13).

Fig. 13: The time of execution of the program *p1.exe*

An Actor can be enveloped into *Composite Actor* that has an extra *runTime* Port as shown in Figure 14.

Fig. 14: Extending an *Expression Actor* into *Composite Actor* with a *runTime* Port

This Actor extension can be removed automatically after the learning process (*learning mode*), to achieve a better workflow performance in the *using mode*. The *copy_of_n* Port is used for joining equivalent Actors into a sequence. In the *design mode* this express the equivalence relation between Actors in the meta-workflow.

The methodology of building, learning and using of workflows is as follows:

- Step 1: expressing a meta-workflow in the *design mode* by a programmer
- Step 2: semiautomatic or full automatic transformations meta-workflow into meta-meta-workflow with enveloping of Actors (i.e. for getting time statistics, adding decision trees etc.)
- Step 3: running and learning this meta-meta-workflow by getting statistic and modify decision trees (*learning mode*)
- Step 4: pruning the meta-meta-workflow into meta-workflow by removing statistic envelopes. This create the *using mode* version of workflow

In case of a change of the computation environment the process of learning can start again and produce a new using mode version of meta-workflow (cf. Figure 15).

Fig. 15: Workflows transformations

5. Algorithms for generating combinatorial objects

5.1. Generating permutations

Let consider the problem of generating all ($n!$) permutations of a sequence of numbers $(1, 2, \dots, n)$. This is an example of the problem where one input parameter produces a lots of output data (cf. Table 1).

Table 1. All permutations for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$

n	output
2	{1,2}
	{2,1}
3	{1,2,3}
	{1,3,2}
	{2,1,3}
	{2,3,1}
	{3,1,2}
	{3,2,1}

We have four *Composite* Actors that generate all permutations (CA_1, CA_2, CA_3, CA_4). To select the best one *Composite* Actor some benchmark tests are needed. If for all tested values of n the runtime ranking is the same then is only one winner, and other Actors can be removed from the workflow. The problem here (cf. Figure 16) is an aggregation of output data, because the same permutation appear many times.

Fig. 16: Getting statistical information about runtime of *Composite* Actors

This problem can be solved by adding hierarchical workflows as a *Meta* Actor where sub-workflow is a sequence of Actors.

Fig. 17: Getting a sequence of runtimes of Actors from a *Meta* Actor

The Actors in the Meta-Actor workflow can be organized in the waterfall schema as is shown in Figure 18.

Fig. 18: A sequence of *Composite Actors* as a *Meta Actor* workflow

In Table 2 are runtimes of *Composite Actors* that generate permutations. It is worth to notices that the best *Composite Actor* (CA₂) was a web-service Actor based on the Prologue. The second best solution was a *Composite Actor* (CA₃) with a Python implementation. The *Composite Actor* (CA₄) was implemented as a RExpression Actor and *Composite Actor* (CA₁) was implemented as a program written in C, but run by the *External Execution Actor*.

Table 2. The runtime ranking of *Composite Actors*

n	The runtimes of Actors
2	{0.078, 0.016, 0.015 , 0.891}
3	{0.063, 0.015, 0.0 , 0.61}
4	{0.063, 0.0 , 0.0 , 0.593}
5	{0.047, 0.015 , 0.016, 0.672}
6	{0.078, 0.0 , 0.125, 1.126}
7	{0.109, 0.047 , 0.328, 12.407}

5.2. Generating graphs

Paper [5] considered a problem of generating of all connected integral graphs of order $n \leq 12$. It used B.D. McKay’s algorithm called *geng* for graphs generating [2]. In the Kepler Project workflow we can use this algorithm to write all graphs as string values to a file, as is shown in Figure 19.

Fig. 19: Using of the *geng* algorithm for generating all graphs of order $n = 5$

In Figure 20 the Kepler Project workflow is shown that generates graphs using the $G(n, p)$ model. In this model the number of graph vertices n is fix, and edges are randomly chosen to the graph with the probability p (cf. Listing 10). If $p = 0.0$, then from the $G(n, p)$ model we obtain a graph without edges. If $p = 1.0$, then we obtain complete graph K_n .

Fig. 20: Usage the $G(n, p)$ model where $n = 6$ and $p = 0.5$

```
L=" "
A <- array(0, dim = c(n,n))
for (i in 1:(n-1))
  for (j in (i+1):n) {
A[i,j] = A[j,i] = (runif(1, 0.0, 1.0) <= p)
if (A[i,j])
  L=paste0(L,"1") else
  L=paste0(L,"0")
}
print <- L
```

Listing 10: The $G(n, p)$ model implementation in the *RExpression* Actor (*Gnp_R*)

```
{0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0; 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1; 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1; 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0; 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0; 0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0}
{0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0; 1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0; 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0; 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0; 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1; 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0}
{0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0; 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0; 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0; 1, 1, 1, 0, 1, 1; 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0; 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0}
{0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0; 1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1; 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1; 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0; 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1; 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0}
{0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1; 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1; 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0; 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1; 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0; 1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0}
```

Listing 11: the *Display 1* Actor: each line is an adjacency matrix of a graph of order $n = 6$

The matrix can be transformed to a list of strings (cf. Listing 12). Each line corresponds to one graph. The elements separated by a space are in the following format: n *code_of_graph* x_1 y_1 x_2 y_2 ... x_n y_n . Values x_i y_i correspond to the position of vertex i in two dimensions. The *code_of_graph* is a string of length $n \cdot (n - 1) / 2$ of '1' and '0' values corresponding to the upper triangle of adjacency matrix of G (cf. Listing 10).

```
6 011100101101000 150 285 266 217 266 82 150 15 33 82 33 217
6 111101100100001 150 285 266 217 266 82 150 15 33 82 33 217
6 011000100100110 150 285 266 217 266 82 150 15 33 82 33 217
6 111100111011001 150 285 266 217 266 82 150 15 33 82 33 217
6 010110010101010 150 285 266 217 266 82 150 15 33 82 33 217
```

Listing 12: Graphs saved in the *poz* format shown in the *Display 2* Actor

6. Prologue database of graphs

```

:- use_module(library(http/thread_httpd)).
:- use_module(library(http/http_dispatch)).
:- use_module(library(http/http_parameters)).
:- http_handler(root(append), new_graph, []).
server(Port) :- http_server(http_dispatch, [port(Port)]).
new_graph(Request) :-
    http_parameters(Request, [g(G, [string])]),
    format('Content-type: text/plain~n~n'),
    (((integral(G)->fail>true), assert(integral(G));true),
    format('~w~n', [G])).

:- http_handler(root(list), list_graph, []).
list_graph(Request) :-
    format('Content-type: text/plain~n~n'),
    findall(G, (integral(G)), X),
    format('~w~n', [X]).

% to run the web-service type in the command line:
% swipl graph_db.pl
% server(5000).
% to add a new graph 111 to database use:
% http://localhost:5000/append?g=111
% to list all graphs in database use:
% http://localhost:5000/list

```

Listing 13: The file *grap_db.pl* – the Prologue implementation of the web-service that stores information about integral graphs

The graphs in the Prologue database [7] can be stored as compound terms with the name of property of G , and the code of graph G as a parameter (i.e. the code '111' corresponds to the complete graph K_3 of order $n = 3$). The main benefit of this representation is that we can also put into the Prologue database some producing rules that add new compound terms derived from the facts in the database.

```

:-dynamic integral/1.
integral('1').
integral('111').
integral('111111').
integral('1111111111').

```

Listing 14: The database of compound terms in the Prologue language corresponding to complete graphs: K_2, K_3, K_4, K_5

Fig. 21: Usage the $G(n, p)$ model and the Prologue database

7. Invariants of graphs

An invariant of the graph G is a value or a vector of values that are identical for any labeling of vertices of graph G (i.e. the number of edges, the sorted degree sequence, the chromatic number, the number of components, the spectrum, the canon labeling).

7.1. The spectrum of graph

The $Sp(G)$ can be calculated using the library function *eigen* from the R Project System (cf. Listing 15). The function *AreInt* tests if graph G is integral. This is fulfilled if all values in $Sp(G)$ are integral.

```
AreR <- function(x) { abs(round(x)-x)<0.0000001 }
AreInt <- function(ev)
{ if (length(ev)>1) {if (AreR(ev[1])) AreInt(ev[2:length(ev)]) else FALSE}
  else AreR(ev[1])
}
ev <- eigen(A) $ values
isIntegral <- AreInt(ev)
```

Listing 15: Usage the R project system for calculating the spectrum of graph G represented by its adjacency matrix A

7.2. The number of components of graph

We can calculate the number of components of graph G using the function *NumOfCom* (cf. Listing 16). This function can be also used for testing if graph G is connected.

```
visited = array(0,c(dim=n))
DFS <-function (nr, B) {
  visited[nr] <- 1
  for (i in 1:n) if (B[nr,i]==1 && visited[i]==0) DFS(i,B)
}
NumOfCom <- function(nr, B) {
  noc <- 0
  for (i in 1:n) { if (visited[i]==0) noc = noc + 1; DFS(i,B)}
  noc
}
isConnected <- (NumOfCom(1,A) == 1)
```

Listing 16: Usage the R Project System for checking if the graph G is connected

8. Workflow for single and multiple data

There is a difference in building the workflow for one big task which we try to divide and run it in parallel, or we have a lot of small tasks in advance. A similar problem is when we go through a workflow only ones and multiple times (i.e. in some loop). Thus, we can test some workflow for one instance of a problem, and then transform this workflow with changing the Director to another one. There is also a possibility to use the *Composite Actor* for single data, and add this *Composite Actor* as a part of workflow for multiple data.

Fig. 22: Usage the *Ramp* Actor

In Figure 22 a Ramp Actor is used as a loop where its output value is incremented by *step* in each firing. The number of firing is limited by the SDF Director.

Fig. 23: Usage the *Ramp* Actor and the PN Director

If we use a PN Director, then the workflow is more complicated. Additional Actors are uses *Expression* Actor and a *Boolean Switch* Actor.

9. Converting data to Tokens

Some Actors produce as output more than one element (i.e. string). If each string is a combinatorial object then to use some other Actors that compute an invariant only for one combinatorial object, we need convert this stream of strings into a sequence of tokens. An example of such transformation is shown in Figure 24. We use there: the *StringSplit* Actor and the *Array to Sequence* Actor. We can also sieve the stream of values under a condition expressed in the *Expression* Actor.

Fig. 24: String to Tokens conversions technique

A similar example is shown in Figure 25. Here, for sieving values we use the *RExpression* Actor and the *Boolean Switch* Actor.

Fig. 25: String to Tokens conversions and data filtering technique using the *RExpression* Actor

10. Actors replication technique

If some calculations for instances of the problem can be done independently then for improving the runtime we can make the replication of the main Actor in the workflow, as is shown in Figure 26. The task for each *Expression* Actors is scheduled under the *Round-Robin* algorithm. Here, the Actor that performs the “main” job is replicated three times (*Expression*, *Expression2*, *Expression5*). The useful limit of the replication can be obtained experimentally.

Fig. 26: The replication of some Actors as a method of speedup of the workflow execution

The replication technique is also a method that can auto-tune workflows for new generations of computers where for each processor more cores will be available. However, this schema of replication has a limit, that comes from the bottleneck of the task scheduler.

We can also introduce in a workflow (cf. Figure 27) a *Map-Reduce* technique. For example we can replicate the *Ramp* Actor and the *Execution* unit (in Figure 22 it is an *Expression* Actor), and split its domain $[0,20]$ into two subdomains $[0,10]$ and $[10,20]$. This split corresponds to a *Map* algorithm and can be done hierarchically. The *Reduce* algorithm can be done by the *Nondeterministic Merge* Actor.

Fig.27: Splitting one *Ramp* Actor into two (or more) *Ramp* Actors

11. Decision trees

Figure 28 shows one of the methods that introduce a *decision tree* (DT) in the Kepler Project workflow. The *Expression* Actor compares vectors of parameters values X of the task with the vector of thresholds values T . It results in a decision class (here the number of algorithms chosen by the *Switch* Actor).

Fig. 28: An example of using the *Expression* Actor as the decision tree (DT)

To build a DT we can use J.R. Quinlan's algorithm called *c4.5*[6]. First, we need to define decision classes and domain of parameters in the file *filename.names* (an example is shown in Listing 18). Here, three classes A , B , C and two continuous parameters n and k are defined.

```
A, B, C.
n: continuous.
```

```
k: continuous.
```

Listing 18: The file *alg1.names* – the example of the input file for the *c4.5* algorithm

We need also to prepare the file *filename.data* with the training set (cf. Listing19). Each line in this file represents: *n, k, decision class*.

```
4,5,A.  
5,6,A.  
6,8,B.  
7,9,B.  
8,8,C.  
9,10,C.
```

Listing 19: The file *alg1.data* – the example of the input file for the *c4.5* algorithm

As an output of the *c4.5* algorithm we obtain the DT shown in Listing 20.

```
k <= 6 : A (2.0)  
k > 6 :  
| n <= 7 : B (2.0)  
| n > 7 : C (2.0)
```

Listing 20: The decision tree obtained from the *c4.5* algorithm

This information can be easily transformed to the DT in the Kepler Project, with following assumptions: a sequence of decision classes (A, B, C) corresponds to a sequence (0, 1, 2), parameters *n* and *k* correspond to $X[0]$ and $X[1]$, and threshold values 6 and 7 correspond to $T[0]$ and $T[1]$. Thus, the DT formula is as follows:

$$X[1] \leq T[0] ? 0 : (X[0] \leq T[1] ? 1 : 2)$$

The native output format of the *c4.5* algorithm is binary. For integration purposes it is better to have a text file. For that reason we define a simple XML format that stores information about the DT obtained from the *c4.5* algorithm. The leaves are names of decision classes. In the node of type *fork*, the first node branch corresponds to fulfill the condition *parameter* \leq *threshold*, the second sub-node corresponds to fulfill the condition *parameter* $>$ *threshold*.

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>  
<dt>  
  <node type="fork">  
    <parameter>k</parameter>  
    <threshold>6</ threshold >  
    <node type="class">  
      <name>A</name>  
    </node>  
    <node type="fork">  
      <parameter>n</parameter>  
      <threshold>7</threshold>  
      <node type="class">  
        <name>B</name>  
      </node>  
      <node type="class">  
        <name>C</name>  
      </node>  
    </node>  
  </node>  
</dt>
```

Listing 21: The decision tree in the XML format

To improve the thresholds in the DT we can during the execution of workflow run additionally in a parallel way another algorithms chosen randomly from the sequence. If it finishes the execution before the algorithm chosen by DT, then we can add this information to the training set, and build a new DT. Instead of choosing another algorithm randomly we can use information about thresholds values. If the parameter value is equal to the threshold value in the node close to leaves of DT than we can run in parallel both branches.

If we distribute computation over the network of heterogeneous hosts, we can also use DT in the job scheduling algorithm to find the best host that can make the fastest computation of our task.

12. Delay execution technique

To improve the performance of the workflow for which it is difficult to predict the runtime, we can use the cascade model of replication. This can be done by a sequence of Actors (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m) that are input/output equivalent, but they are different in the time execution and the overhead (i.e. connected with task dividing, distribution, and results aggregation). First, we fire the Actor A_1 that can be slow, but for them overhead is the lowest. We add also to the scheduler a copy of the task with the next Actor A_2 , but in this case we introduce the delay of start (cf. Figure 29). If the first algorithm realized by Actor A_1 finishes its task before delay, than a copy of the task A_2 can be removed from the scheduler queue or signal this task to kill if it is running. When the second Actor A_2 is starting it puts the next copy of the task with the Actor A_3 into the queue of scheduler with a bigger delay.

Fig. 29: An example of using the *DelayStart* Actor

The same strategy can be used in the case when the task can be divided into two or more parts (subtasks). In case when one big task is working too long, we can run in the delay technique its equivalent subtasks. This can be done hierarchically for subtasks.

13. Prologue database of running and completed jobs

The process of generating combinatorial objects can be speedup by the search space partition or tasks partition. If it is a hierarchical partition there is a problem how to control the job status and detecting if all tasks are finished. During the generating process some of tasks may be lost, so it is worth to having information about completed tasks. Then, we can run only the missing part of computation. For example if we use the *gen* algorithm we can notify the Prologue database, that generates all graphs on $n = 5$ vertices started by asserting the compound term *running(5)* to the Prologue database. If this process is finished, we notify the Prologue database by asserting the term *completed(5)*, and retract term *running(5)*. If we are interested in all running processes we can ask the Prologue database putting from the console the question *running(N)*. Then, when some tasks are running (i.e. $n = 5$ and $n = 6$) we obtain from the Prologue database two answers: $N = 5$ and $N = 6$.

If the search space is partitioned into m subspaces, then generating can be run independently as m subtasks. In the database we can then assert a rule (i.e. *completed(3) :- completed(3,0), completed(3,1), completed(3,2), completed(3,3)*) that give us answer *true* only in the case when all subtasks (i.e. generating graphs in classes with a fixed number of edges) are finished. Thus, using the Prologue databases we can provide some extra features that are not directly available in the standard SQL databases.

14. Conclusions

The Kepler Project is a tool that can help users and programmers to express in the graphical way a complex problem of generating combinatorial objects. Usually this process has many inter-medial steps. It can also help to test and check correctness of new algorithms comparison with old ones. This is also the platform for integrating different techniques, i.e. the R Project module, the Python module, Actors written in Java, web-

services and others. This general model of designing workflow can be easily extended by the users (i.e. adding new Directors).

Workflows can also be viewed as a special kind of a code, that can be run, tested and then transformed to another formal programming language, then compiled to a new programme and then executed faster. On the other hand, workflow is also a graph that we can find by generating combinatorial structures, transform it, and test some structural and dynamic properties to find the best solution for a current computational environment.

There are also some disadvantages of the Kepler Project, i.e. it is difficult to introduce and distribute more complicated data structures than arrays and matrices in the workflow. There is also no possibility to comment Actors (with a consequence that some links connected with this Actor are temporally removed from the workflow).

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